

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK H M** bearing USN **3SU18SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYA C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU18SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMBRAS MOHAMMED P K** bearing USN **3SU18SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSHREE R** bearing USN **3SU18SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHISH KRISHNA P** bearing USN **3SU18SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHITH SHETTY K** bearing USN **3SU18SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANYA OMANAKUTTAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA SUHANA I** bearing USN **3SU18SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK R SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU18SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KHADER ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU18SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LARISA PHAWA** bearing USN **3SU18SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAFWAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAHRAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAYAD AFREEDI** bearing USN **3SU18SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HANEEFA** bearing USN **3SU18SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED IRFAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUHAJIR B** bearing USN **3SU18SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NOUFAL** bearing USN **3SU18SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SALMAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SARFARAZ** bearing USN **3SU18SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA SHAREEF** bearing USN **3SU18SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ALFAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PAWAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PISAVADIYA CHANDNI BEN BHARATBHAI** bearing USN **3SU18SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POORNASHREE K V** bearing USN **3SU18SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHAM** bearing USN **3SU18SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHEEK P ACHAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAAM KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU18SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJA KUMAR SAH** bearing USN **3SU18SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJITH VK** bearing USN **3SU18SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAZIN LATHEEF P P** bearing USN **3SU18SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SACHIN M** bearing USN **3SU18SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHRA M** bearing USN **3SU18SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHITHIN SREEJITH** bearing USN **3SU18SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAJESH SOMAYAJI** bearing USN **3SU18SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREYA PRAKASH HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UCHIL NINAD SACHINDRA** bearing USN **3SU18SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UM AQEEL ISMAIL** bearing USN **3SU18SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAMEEZ** bearing USN **3SU18CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHABEER.A** bearing USN **3SU18CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY HAREENDRAN** bearing USN **3SU18CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALDRIN FLAXON DSOUZA** bearing USN **3SU18CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DAKSHAYANI P.K** bearing USN **3SU18CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU18CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FAKRUDDIN RAHIF** bearing USN **3SU18CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNA B** bearing USN **3SU18CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JAISHANKAR** bearing USN **3SU18CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JESVITA MELISHA MENDONCA** bearing USN **3SU18CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHESH SB** bearing USN **3SU18CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK N K** bearing USN **3SU18CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA LAKSHMN M** bearing USN **3SU18CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAVANYA HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SHAFEER** bearing USN **3SU18CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ISHAM** bearing USN **3SU18CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD NAWAZ SAJJAD** bearing USN **3SU18CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUCHALLI MUNI DIMPLE** bearing USN **3SU18CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMIL A P** bearing USN **3SU18CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHEESH PRAKASHAN PARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU18CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **REGO STEWART SEDRIC ANTON** bearing USN **3SU18CI021** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK H M** bearing USN **3SU18SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYA C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU18SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMBRAS MOHAMMED P K** bearing USN **3SU18SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSHREE R** bearing USN **3SU18SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHISH KRISHNA P** bearing USN **3SU18SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHITH SHETTY K** bearing USN **3SU18SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANYA OMANAKUTTAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA SUHANA I** bearing USN **3SU18SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK R SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU18SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KHADER ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU18SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LARISA PHAWA** bearing USN **3SU18SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAFWAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAHRAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAYAD AFREEDI** bearing USN **3SU18SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HANEEFA** bearing USN **3SU18SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED IRFAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUHAJIR B** bearing USN **3SU18SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NOUFAL** bearing USN **3SU18SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SALMAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SARFARAZ** bearing USN **3SU18SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA SHAREEF** bearing USN **3SU18SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ALFAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PAWAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PISAVADIYA CHANDNI BEN BHARATBHAI** bearing USN **3SU18SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POORNASHREE K V** bearing USN **3SU18SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHAM** bearing USN **3SU18SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHEEK P ACHAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAAM KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU18SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJA KUMAR SAH** bearing USN **3SU18SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJITH VK** bearing USN **3SU18SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAZIN LATHEEF P P** bearing USN **3SU18SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SACHIN M** bearing USN **3SU18SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHRA M** bearing USN **3SU18SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHITHIN SREEJITH** bearing USN **3SU18SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAJESH SOMAYAJI** bearing USN **3SU18SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREYA PRAKASH HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UCHIL NINAD SACHINDRA** bearing USN **3SU18SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UM AQEEL ISMAIL** bearing USN **3SU18SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAMEEZ** bearing USN **3SU18CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHABEER.A** bearing USN **3SU18CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY HAREENDRAN** bearing USN **3SU18CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALDRIN FLAXON DSOUZA** bearing USN **3SU18CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DAKSHAYANI P.K** bearing USN **3SU18CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU18CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FAKRUDDIN RAHIF** bearing USN **3SU18CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNA B** bearing USN **3SU18CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JAISHANKAR** bearing USN **3SU18CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JESVITA MELISHA MENDONCA** bearing USN **3SU18CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITESH SB** bearing USN **3SU18CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK N K** bearing USN **3SU18CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA LAKSHMN M** bearing USN **3SU18CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAVANYA HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SHAFEER** bearing USN **3SU18CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ISHAM** bearing USN **3SU18CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD NAWAZ SAJJAD** bearing USN **3SU18CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUCHALLI MUNI DIMPLE** bearing USN **3SU18CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMIL A P** bearing USN **3SU18CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHEESH PRAKASHAN PARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU18CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **REGO STEWART SEDRIC ANTON** bearing USN **3SU18CI021** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK H M** bearing USN **3SU18SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYA C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU18SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMBRAS MOHAMMED P K** bearing USN **3SU18SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSHREE R** bearing USN **3SU18SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHISH KRISHNA P** bearing USN **3SU18SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHITH SHETTY K** bearing USN **3SU18SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANYA OMANAKUTTAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA SUHANA I** bearing USN **3SU18SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK R SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU18SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KHADER ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU18SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LARISA PHAWA** bearing USN **3SU18SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAFWAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAHRAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAYAD AFREEDI** bearing USN **3SU18SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HANEEFA** bearing USN **3SU18SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED IRFAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUHAJIR B** bearing USN **3SU18SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NOUFAL** bearing USN **3SU18SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SALMAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SARFARAZ** bearing USN **3SU18SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA SHAREEF** bearing USN **3SU18SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ALFAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PAWAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PISAVADIYA CHANDNI BEN BHARATBHAI** bearing USN **3SU18SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POORNASHREE K V** bearing USN **3SU18SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHAM** bearing USN **3SU18SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHEEK P ACHAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAAM KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU18SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJA KUMAR SAH** bearing USN **3SU18SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJITH VK** bearing USN **3SU18SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAZIN LATHEEF P P** bearing USN **3SU18SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SACHIN M** bearing USN **3SU18SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHRA M** bearing USN **3SU18SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHITHIN SREEJITH** bearing USN **3SU18SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAJESH SOMAYAJI** bearing USN **3SU18SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREYA PRAKASH HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UCHIL NINAD SACHINDRA** bearing USN **3SU18SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UM AQEEL ISMAIL** bearing USN **3SU18SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAMEEZ** bearing USN **3SU18CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHABEER.A** bearing USN **3SU18CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY HAREENDRAN** bearing USN **3SU18CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALDRIN FLAXON DSOUZA** bearing USN **3SU18CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DAKSHAYANI P.K** bearing USN **3SU18CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU18CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FAKRUDDIN RAHIF** bearing USN **3SU18CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNA B** bearing USN **3SU18CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JAISHANKAR** bearing USN **3SU18CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JESVITA MELISHA MENDONCA** bearing USN **3SU18CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHESH SB** bearing USN **3SU18CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK N K** bearing USN **3SU18CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA LAKSHMN M** bearing USN **3SU18CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAVANYA HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SHAFEER** bearing USN **3SU18CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ISHAM** bearing USN **3SU18CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD NAWAZ SAJJAD** bearing USN **3SU18CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUCHALLI MUNI DIMPLE** bearing USN **3SU18CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMIL A P** bearing USN **3SU18CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHEESH PRAKASHAN PARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU18CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **REGO STEWART SEDRIC ANTON** bearing USN **3SU18CI021** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK H M** bearing USN **3SU18SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYA C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU18SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMBRAS MOHAMMED P K** bearing USN **3SU18SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSHREE R** bearing USN **3SU18SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHISH KRISHNA P** bearing USN **3SU18SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHITH SHETTY K** bearing USN **3SU18SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANYA OMANAKUTTAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA SUHANA I** bearing USN **3SU18SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK R SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU18SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KHADER ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU18SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LARISA PHAWA** bearing USN **3SU18SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAFWAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAHRAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAYAD AFREEDI** bearing USN **3SU18SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HANEEFA** bearing USN **3SU18SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED IRFAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUHAJIR B** bearing USN **3SU18SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NOUFAL** bearing USN **3SU18SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SALMAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SARFARAZ** bearing USN **3SU18SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA SHAREEF** bearing USN **3SU18SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ALFAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PAWAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PISAVADIYA CHANDNI BEN BHARATBHAI** bearing USN **3SU18SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the IV SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POORNASHREE K V** bearing USN **3SU18SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHAM** bearing USN **3SU18SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHEEK P ACHAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAAM KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU18SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJA KUMAR SAH** bearing USN **3SU18SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJITH VK** bearing USN **3SU18SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAZIN LATHEEF P P** bearing USN **3SU18SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SACHIN M** bearing USN **3SU18SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHRA M** bearing USN **3SU18SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHITHIN SREEJITH** bearing USN **3SU18SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAJESH SOMAYAJI** bearing USN **3SU18SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREYA PRAKASH HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UCHIL NINAD SACHINDRA** bearing USN **3SU18SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UM AQEEL ISMAIL** bearing USN **3SU18SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAMEEZ** bearing USN **3SU18CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHABEER.A** bearing USN **3SU18CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY HAREENDRAN** bearing USN **3SU18CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALDRIN FLAXON DSOUZA** bearing USN **3SU18CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DAKSHAYANI P.K** bearing USN **3SU18CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU18CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FAKRUDDIN RAHIF** bearing USN **3SU18CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNA B** bearing USN **3SU18CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JAISHANKAR** bearing USN **3SU18CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JESVITA MELISHA MENDONCA** bearing USN **3SU18CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHESH SB** bearing USN **3SU18CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK N K** bearing USN **3SU18CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA LAKSHMN M** bearing USN **3SU18CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAVANYA HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SHAFEER** bearing USN **3SU18CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ISHAM** bearing USN **3SU18CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD NAWAZ SAJJAD** bearing USN **3SU18CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUCHALLI MUNI DIMPLE** bearing USN **3SU18CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMIL A P** bearing USN **3SU18CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHEESH PRAKASHAN PARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU18CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **REGO STEWART SEDRIC ANTON** bearing USN **3SU18CI021** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK H M** bearing USN **3SU18SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYA C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU18SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMBRAS MOHAMMED P K** bearing USN **3SU18SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANUSHREE R** bearing USN **3SU18SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHISH KRISHNA P** bearing USN **3SU18SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHITH SHETTY K** bearing USN **3SU18SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANYA OMANAKUTTAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FATHIMA SUHANA I** bearing USN **3SU18SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK R SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU18SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KHADER ASHIQ** bearing USN **3SU18SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LARISA PHAWA** bearing USN **3SU18SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAFWAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAHRAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAYAD AFREEDI** bearing USN **3SU18SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED HANEEFA** bearing USN **3SU18SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED IRFAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MUHAJIR B** bearing USN **3SU18SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED NOUFAL** bearing USN **3SU18SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SALMAN** bearing USN **3SU18SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SARFAZ** bearing USN **3SU18SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA SHAREEF** bearing USN **3SU18SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED ALFAS** bearing USN **3SU18SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PAWAN KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PISAVADIYA CHANDNI BEN BHARATBHAI** bearing USN **3SU18SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **POORNASHREE K V** bearing USN **3SU18SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHAM** bearing USN **3SU18SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHEEK P ACHAR** bearing USN **3SU18SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAAM KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU18SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJA KUMAR SAH** bearing USN **3SU18SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAJITH VK** bearing USN **3SU18SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAZIN LATHEEF P P** bearing USN **3SU18SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SACHIN M** bearing USN **3SU18SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHRA M** bearing USN **3SU18SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHITHIN SREEJITH** bearing USN **3SU18SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREERAJESH SOMAYAJI** bearing USN **3SU18SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREYA PRAKASH HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UCHIL NINAD SACHINDRA** bearing USN **3SU18SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **UM AQEEL ISMAIL** bearing USN **3SU18SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAMEEZ** bearing USN **3SU18CI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHABEER.A** bearing USN **3SU18CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY HAREENDRAN** bearing USN **3SU18CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALDRIN FLAXON DSOUZA** bearing USN **3SU18CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DAKSHAYANI P.K** bearing USN **3SU18CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU18CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FAKRUDDIN RAHIF** bearing USN **3SU18CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARIKRISHNA B** bearing USN **3SU18CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JAISHANKAR** bearing USN **3SU18CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JESVITA MELISHA MENDONCA** bearing USN **3SU18CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JITHESH SB** bearing USN **3SU18CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK N K** bearing USN **3SU18CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA LAKSHMN M** bearing USN **3SU18CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAVANYA HEGDE** bearing USN **3SU18CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SHAFEER** bearing USN **3SU18CI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ISHAM** bearing USN **3SU18CI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD NAWAZ SAJJAD** bearing USN **3SU18CI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUCHALLI MUNI DIMPLE** bearing USN **3SU18CI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SHAMIL A P** bearing USN **3SU18CI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NITHEESH PRAKASHAN PARAYIL** bearing USN **3SU18CI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Mangalore
Institute of Computer Science and Information Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **REGO STEWART SEDRIC ANTON** bearing USN **3SU18CI021** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

Dean, CCSIS
DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001